

Rational design of N3-Bromo benzyl noscapine as a promising derivative of the natural lead molecule, noscapine with improved cytotoxicity effects on breast cancer cell lines

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ABSTRACT

We present a new derivative of a natural lead molecule, noscapine by coupling the 3-bromo benzyl functional group with the 'N' atom in the scaffold to develop N3-Bromo benzyl noscapine (N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos) on the basis of our in silico efforts. On the basis of the combination of molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulation studies, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was found to have better binding affinity towards tubulin, with a docking score of -6.727 kcal/mol, than did noscapine (-4.080 kcal/mol), and with an improved binding free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$) of -25.50 kcal/mol, than noscapine ($\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ was -22.93 kcal/mol). Inspired by our in silico calculation, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was chemically synthesized, and its anticancer activity was validated based on cellular studies using two human breast cancer cell lines, MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 and a normal healthy cell line (HEK). The compound N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos revealed IC₅₀ values of 7.51 μM and 12.12 μM , respectively, without causing any toxicity to normal cells (IC₅₀ value is 215 μM). The induction of apoptosis was analysed via FACS. Moreover, the onset of apoptosis in MDA-MB-231 cells by the treatment of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos revealed morphological changes such as cellular shrinkage, chromatin condensation, membrane blebbing, and apoptotic body formation. Along with elevated reactive oxygen species (ROS), there was a loss of mitochondrial membrane potential, suggesting the induction of cancer cell apoptosis. Additionally, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos significantly inhibited the growth of the spheroids. These

results imply that the newly designed N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos has impressive anticancer activity against breast cancer cell lines and has possible therapeutic option for the treatment of breast cancer.

Keywords: Noscapine, MD simulation, Apoptosis, ROS; N-Bromo benzyl noscapine

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the world's top causes of mortality and remains a severe threat to global health after cardiovascular disorders. As per the World Health Organization (WHO) estimate, by 2040, 29.4 million new instances of cancer will be identified worldwide (Lee *et al.*, 2024). Several human tumors have been successfully treated with microtubule-targeting chemotherapeutics, such as vinca alkaloids and taxol derivatives. However, the therapeutic use of these compounds has been associated with several limitations due to their poor solubility and severe toxicity (especially peripheral neuropathies, gastrointestinal toxicity, myelosuppression, and immunosuppression) (Ye *et al.*, 1998; Landen *et al.*, 2002; Zhou, Gupta, *et al.*, 2002; Zhou, Panda, *et al.*, 2002; Checchi *et al.*, 2003; Zhou *et al.*, 2003; Aneja, Vangapandu, Lopus, Chandra, *et al.*, 2006; Aneja, Vangapandu, Lopus, Viswesarappa, *et al.*, 2006; Joshi *et al.*, 2010). However, the success of taxol in the management of aggressive breast and ovarian cancers has encouraged the identification of other compounds that target microtubules but are less toxic, soluble in aqueous solutions and substantially effective both alone and in combination with currently available drugs such as docetaxel. Among the several antimitotic compounds, Noscapine is an excellent therapeutic choice that is not toxic to healthy cells (Ye *et al.*, 1998; Landen *et al.*, 2002; Zhou *et al.*, 2002). It inhibits the kinetics of microtubule assembly and cell cycle progression during mitosis, resulting in apoptotic cell death in a wide range of carcinoma cells (Ye *et al.*, 1998; Landen *et al.*, 2002; Zhou *et al.*, 2002). This is an important feature over widely accessible antimicrotubular drugs, which either hinder microtubule disintegration (taxanes, epothilone) or inhibit the assembly of tubulin (vincas, eribulin, estramustine) and therefore do not trigger any hemotoxicity or neuronal toxicity.

To improve further the anticancer activity of noscapine, several derivatives have been designed and chemically synthesized (known as noscapinoids). Some of these derivatives have shown better pharmacological profiles than the parent compound. Briefly, more than three generations of noscapinoids have been developed,

and their chemical synthesis and anticancer activities have been experimentally studied in cancer cells of different tissue origins (Aneja, Vangapandu, Lopus, Chandra, *et al.*, 2006; Naik *et al.*, 2011; Santoshi *et al.*, 2011). These generations of noscapinoids represent chemical modifications of the functional groups of noscapine that have been demonstrated to significantly attenuate its biological activity. While several synthetic analogues of noscapine have demonstrated efficacy against tumor cell lines, even at higher doses, they are not able to significantly regress the implanted tumor in xenograft model. In our continuous effort to make new derivatives of noscapine, we present in this study a new derivative of noscapine, namely, N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine (N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos). This derivative was found to have more promising activity than the lead molecule.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Development of N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine

A new molecule, N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine (N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos), was designed by coupling the 3-bromo benzyl functional group with the 'N' atom of the noscapine scaffold. This is mainly because the addition of different functional groups at the 'N' atom in the noscapine scaffold was reported earlier for the development of promising derivatives with improved binding affinity with tubulin and antiproliferative activity (Santoshi *et al.*, 2011; Naik *et al.*, 2012; Santoshi *et al.*, 2015; Patel *et al.*, 2021; Pragyandipta *et al.*, 2021; Pragyandipta *et al.*, 2022; Ravi Kumar Pedapati *et al.*, 2023; Pragyandipta, Naik, *et al.*, 2023; Pragyandipta, Pedapati, *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, bromobenzyl derivatives are often used in drug design because of the electronic and steric effects they can introduce. The 3-bromobenzyl group can modulate receptor affinity, membrane permeability, and metabolic stability.

2.2 In silico prediction of binding affinity of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos

2.2.1 Tubulin heterodimer protein optimization

The high-resolution (2.20 Å) X-ray crystallography cocomplex structure of microtubules and amino

noscapine was downloaded from the protein structure database (PDB ID: 6Y6D). The multistep protein preparation wizard of the Schrödinger software package (Schrödinger, Inc., NY) was utilized to prepare the cocomplex structure by adding missing hydrogen, assigning protonation states to amino acids, assigning bond orders to atoms, etc. The missing side chain atoms were identified and fixed using the Prime tool (Schrödinger, Inc., NY). Finally, MacroModel was used to optimize the protein by minimizing its energy.

2.2.2 Preparation of the molecular structure of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos

The molecular structure of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was built using ChemDraw. The structure was then loaded into Maestro (Schrödinger, Inc., NY), and the energy was minimized using MacroModel (Schrödinger, Inc., NY) with the OPLS 2005 force field and the PRCG algorithm. The energy gradient used was 0.001 kcal/mol. As previously described, geometric optimization was performed using Jaguar (Schrödinger, Inc., NY) (Pragyandipta, Pedapati, *et al.*, 2023). Finally, LigPrep (Schrödinger, Inc., NY) was used to generate various conformations of the molecule.

2.2.3 Molecular docking

Molecular docking of noscapine and its derivative, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos, onto the $\alpha\beta$ -tubulin heterodimer was performed using Glide XP algorithm (Schrödinger, Inc., NY). The noscapinoid binding site was specified by creating two grid boxes around it. An inner grid box of size 14 Å × 14 Å × 14 Å was defined at the centroid of the binding site by selecting the cocomplex ligand amino-noscapine using the Glide grid-receptor generation program. This box defines the search space in which the diameter midpoint of each docked ligand must be present. Furthermore, an outer grid box was also defined with a size of ≤ 24 Å for the cocomplexed ligand, amino noscapine. It defines the volume within which all ligand atoms of a valid pose must be located. Molecule docking of noscapine and its derivative, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos, was performed by Glide-XP algorithm (Thomas A Halgren *et al.*, 2004) using Schrödinger package, and their binding poses were evaluated by Glide XP_{Score} function (Richard A Friesner *et al.*, 2004; Thomas A Halgren *et al.*, 2004). For the ligand docking method, a scale factor of 0.4 for van der Waals radii was implemented for protein atoms with exact partial charges less than or equal to 0.25. Out of the 10000

poses sampled, 1000 were extracted by minimization (conjugate gradients), and favourable Glide docking performance was further evaluated by 30 structures with the lowest energy conformation. The single best conformation for each ligand was used for further analysis.

2.2.4 MD simulation

The docked complexes of (a) noscapine and (b) N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos with the $\alpha\beta$ -tubulin heterodimer along with GTP, GDP, and magnesium were considered for molecular dynamics (MD) simulations using GROMACS version 2019.2. GROMACS uses the Amber99SB force field to analyse the protein to obtain the coordinates and topology (Hornak *et al.*, 2006). The general Amber force field (GAFF) was used to determine the parameters for the GTP, GDP, and ligands (Wang *et al.*, 2004), and the AM1-BCC charge model was used to assign atomic point charges (Jakalian *et al.*, 2002). The leap tool in Amber 18 and the ACPYPE system (Sousa da Silva & Vranken, 2012) were used to generate topologies and internal coordinates for all the ligands, maintaining a distance of 12 Å between the protein atoms and the walls of the truncated octahedron box for solvation, and TIP3P was used as a water model. The molecular dynamics modelling of a tubulin complex with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos in the presence of GTP, GDP, and magnesium was the focus of this investigation. Energy minimization and NVT/NPT runs were used to equilibrate the system using the Amber99SB force field. Stability was evaluated using metrics such as the RMSD and RMSF in a 100 ns simulation, and the binding process was examined by determining which conformation from the trajectory had the lowest energy.

2.2.5 Prediction of the binding free energy using MM-PBSA technique

The binding free energy of noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos with the $\alpha\beta$ -tubulin heterodimer was determined using the MM-PBSA method. During the last 10 ns of the molecular dynamics simulation, 500 snapshots were collected at 20 ps intervals. We have used the g_mmpbsa programme to predict the average binding free energy $\Delta G_{bind, pred}$ (Kumari *et al.*, 2014; Pedapati *et al.*, 2023) as follows:

$$\Delta G_{bind, pred} = \Delta G_{complex} - [\Delta G_{Rec} + \Delta G_{lig}]$$

$$G = E_{gas} + G_{sol} - TS.$$

$$E_{gas} = E_{int} + E_{ele} + E_{vdw}$$

$$G_{\text{sol}} = G_{\text{PB(GB)}} + G_{\text{sol-np}}$$

$$G_{\text{sol-np}} = \gamma \text{SAS}$$

The gas phase energy (E_{gas}), which combines internal, electrostatic, and van der Waals energies, is one of the energy components that constitute Gibbs free energy (G). Polar (GPB) and nonpolar ($G_{\text{sol-np}}$) contributions are used to calculate the solvation-free energy; the latter is associated with the solvent-accessible surface area (SAS). Owing to their superior docking scores over noscapine and high binding affinity for tubulin, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was chemically synthesised for experimental evaluation.

2.3 Chemical synthesis of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos

The compound N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was chemically synthesized according to the following

Reaction Scheme: Synthesis of N-3-Br benzyl noscapine: (i) a: *m*-CPBA, DCM; b: 2 N HCl; C: FeSO₄.7H₂O; (ii) 3-Bromo benzyl bromide, KI, K₂CO₃, acetone, RT, 97%.

The starting solution of (S)-6,7-dimethoxy-3-((R)-4-methoxy-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]isoquinolin-5-yl)isobenzofuran-1(3H)-one (200 mg, 0.50 mmol) in acetone (5 mL), was added to potassium carbonate (1.10 mmol), potassium iodide (0.5 mmol) and 3-bromo benzyl bromide (0.55 mmol) and stirred at room temperature (RT) for 1 h. The crude reaction mixture was filtered and evaporated under vacuum, water (5 mL) and dichloromethane (2 X 10 mL) were added, and the organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was purified by the silica gel column chromatography with hexane/ethyl acetate (70:30) to yield a solid product.

(S)-3-((R)-6-(3-bromobenzyl)-4-methoxy-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]isoquinolin-5-yl)-6,7-dimethoxyisobenzofuran-1(3H)-one:

Yield: 97%; mp 65 °C; [α]_{D25} = 52.0 (*c* = 1, dichloromethane); IR ν_{max} (cm⁻¹): 3503, 2940, 2837, 1759, 1621, 1498, 1387, 1271, 1212, 1039, 891, 785, 695. ¹H NMR: (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.40-7.30 (m, 2H), 7.24-7.09 (m, 2H),

reaction scheme. Reactions were regulated by thin-layer chromatography (precoated silica plates and visualization under UV light). All the intermediates and final products were structurally characterized by ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra in CDCl₃ on AVANCE-300 MHz, 400 MHz, and 500 MHz spectrometers. The high-resolution spectra were recorded with an ESI source (IICT, Hyderabad) on a QSTAR XL hybrid MS/MS system (Applied Biosystems/MDS Sciex, Foster City, USA). Column chromatography was carried out in standard silica gel (60–120 mesh). The final product was HPLC purified (purity > 96%). The ¹³C NMR spectra and the ESI mass spectral data of the final product N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos are included in the supporting material in the appendix.

6.99 (d, *J* = 8.30 Hz, 1H), 6.34 (s, 1H), 6.15 (d, *J* = 8.30 Hz, 1H), 5.95 (s, 2H), 5.66 (d, *J* = 3.96 Hz, 1H), 4.60 (d, *J* = 3.96 Hz, 1H), 4.17-4.06 (m, 4H), 4.04 (s, 3H) 3.87, (s, 3H), 3.63 (d, *J* = 13.78 Hz, 1H), 2.50-2.37 (m, 2H), 2.32-2.19 (m, 1H), 2.07-1.92 (m, 1H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 168.1, 152.2, 148.5, 147.9, 141.5, 140.4, 134.0, 131.8, 131.4, 130.0, 129.7, 127.3, 122.2, 118.1, 117.7, 116.6, 102.4, 100.7, 81.6, 81.1, 62.5, 61.1, 59.5, 59.3, 56.7, 45.4, 26.8. MS (ESI) *m/z* 568 [M+H]⁺. HRMS (ESI) Calcd for C₂₈H₂₆BrNO₇ [M+H]⁺: 568.41, found: 568.41.

2.4 Chemicals and reagents

Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) (Gibco BRL, UK), fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Gibco BRL, UK), 10X phosphate buffer saline (Gibco BRL, UK), 0.25%, EDTA 0.003% (Gibco BRL, UK), 10 mg/mL penicillin/streptomycin solution (Sigma-Aldrich), DMSO (HIMEDIA), (S, R)-noscapine (Sigma-Aldrich), 4% paraformaldehyde solution (Himedia), Hoechst 3334 (trihydrochloride, trihydrate) (Invitrogen), crystal violet (Himedia), 3-(4,5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium

m bromide (Hi-AR™) were used in this study for cell culture and treatment. All other chemicals were also of analytical grade and exhibited the highest purity. Human breast cancer cell lines (MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7) and a human embryonic kidney cell line (HEK-293), which were obtained from NCCS, Pune, were maintained and cultured in a humidified incubator at 37 °C with 5% CO₂. All laboratory procedures were conducted within a Class A2 biosafety cabinet, ensuring strict aseptic conditions.

2.5 Cell lines and culture

The human breast cancer cell line MCF-7 was acquired from the cell registry of the National Centre for Cell Science in Pune, Maharashtra, India. The cells were grown in 5% CO₂ and 95% humidity in Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM, Pan Biotech) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) and antibiotics at a favourable temperature of 37 °C. For bioassays using trypsin-EDTA (0.25%), 70–80% confluent cells were subcultured. The cells at 70–80% confluence were subcultured with trypsin-EDTA (0.25%) for assays.

2.6 Cell viability assay

The cell proliferation activity was determined using the MTT assay (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide). In brief, 5 × 10³ cells/well were seeded into 96-well plates with the desired drug concentration, followed by a 48-hour incubation period. After incubation the cells were treated with MTT solution (5 mg/ml) under light-protected conditions for 3–4 h at 37 °C. The absorbance thereafter was determined at 570 nm using a plate reader. The IC₅₀ values of the drugs were calculated using GraphPad. All the experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.7 Flow cytometry analysis for the apoptosis assay

The annexin V-FITC method was used to distinguish necrotic and apoptotic cells to assess apoptosis. After treatment, the cells were incubated with 100 μL of annexin binding buffer after being washed with ice-cold PBS. After adding Annexin V-FITC (2 μg/mL), the mixture was incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature in the dark. After adding annexin binding buffer and 5 μL of PI (0.5 mg/mL), the

percentage of cell death in the treated and control groups was measured.

2.8 Measurement of reactive oxygen species

Apoptosis may be triggered by intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), which are essential for damaging organelles, lipid membranes, and nucleic acids. The fluorescent probe 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate (DCFDA) oxidizes to 2,7-dichlorofluorescein (DCF) in presence of oxygen radicals and emits green fluorescence, was used to measure the generation of ROS. The cells were first cultured on 6-well plates and exposed to N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos for four hours. The generation of intracellular ROS levels was measured using the DCFDA assay. While the control group presented little green fluorescence, the treated cells presented a significant increase in bright green fluorescence following DCFDA staining, which was visible under a Nikon Eclipse Ts2R-FL fluorescence microscope. The results revealed that the intracellular ROS levels significantly increased in the treated cells.

2.9 Measurement of the mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$)

A cationic dye called JC-1 is used to evaluate the depolarization of mitochondria. For 12 hours, the cells were exposed to the drug at an IC₅₀ concentration. Following washing with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), the cells were treated with JC-1 for 30 minutes at room temperature. A Nikon Eclipse Ts2R-FL fluorescence microscope was used to detect the membrane potential of the mitochondria. The emission change from red to green revealed damage to the mitochondria and a loss of membrane integrity.

2.10 Morphological analysis using DAPI, EtBr & AO

Briefly, MCF7 cells were grown on coverslips coated with poly-L-lysine in 6-well plates and treated with the IC₅₀ concentration of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. Then, the cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde and stained with DAPI, EtBr & AO. Morphological alterations in the control and treated cells were observed using a fluorescent microscope. The apoptotic cells were determined on the basis of nuclear condensation, the formation of apoptotic bodies and membrane blebbing.

2.11 Colony formation assay

Colony formation ability was evaluated using clonogenic analysis. In six-well plates, 300 MCF-7 cells were seeded in each well and incubated for 24 h. After incubation, the cells were treated with the IC₅₀ and IC₇₀ concentrations of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos for 24 h. The next day, the media was replaced with fresh media. The cells were incubated for 10–12 days by maintaining the culture conditions in a CO₂ incubator to allow the cancer cells to form colonies. Crystal violet and 4% paraformaldehyde solutions were used to fix and stain the colonies. Moreover, the number of colonies was calculated using image J software.

2.12 Assessment of cell migration

An in vitro migration test was performed to assess cell migration. In six-well plates, 1 × 10³ MDA-MB-231 cells were plated. Following 80% confluency, the cultures were treated with the IC₅₀ concentration of the drug after a scratch was made in each well using a 200 µl pipette tip. A microscope was used to take pictures of the scratched regions at 0 and 48 hours, and the ratio of the thickness of the wound before and after treatment was used to determine the percentage of wound closure.

2.13 Spheroid formation

Briefly, 5000 cells/well (MDA-MB-231) were grown in a 96-well round-bottom cell culture plate, trypsinized, and then centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5 minutes to unite all the cells to create a single spheroid. The cellular microcomplex was cultured at 37 °C with a 5% CO₂ supply under conventional cell culture conditions for four to five days. Phase contrast microscopy was used to track the spheroids over time. Additionally, for 48 hours, the spheroids were exposed to an IC₅₀ concentration of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. The following formula was used to determine the average volume of the spheroids: $V = (4/3) \pi R^3$.

2.14 Statistical analysis

All the experiments were performed in triplicate, and the data are presented as the means ± standard errors of the means. One-way ANOVA was performed using GraphPad Prism software. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Molecular docking and MD simulation of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos

The molecular docking of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapiine, was performed using Glide Xp as reported earlier (Pedapati *et al.*, 2023). The molecules showed good binding at the binding site. The Glide XP_{score} function (R. A. Friesner *et al.*, 2004; T. A. Halgren *et al.*, 2004; Pedapati *et al.*, 2023) was used to determine the binding affinity with tubulin. The N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos revealed improved docking results of -6.727 kcal/mol compared with that of noscapiine (docking score of -4.080 kcal/mol) (Table 1). Furthermore, the docked complexes of these ligands with tubulin were subjected to MD simulation (100 ns) to evaluate the stability of the complexes. The RMSD and Rg of the backbone C_α atoms with respect to time were analysed by plotting the convergence of the MD sequential snapshots. The relative variations in the RMSD (0.21 to 2.24 Å) and Rg (29.8 to 30.5 Å) were minimal, suggesting system stability (Fig. 1a&b). Furthermore, to illustrate the importance of these residues, the RMSF of tubulin in both the free form and the bound form with ligands was calculated (Fig. 2a&b). The RMSF value of the residues was found to be minimal (1.5 to 3.5 Å) in both the bound and free forms for both α- and β-tubulin, revealing the rigidity of the residues. Moreover, the N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapiine were well accommodated within the binding site, i.e., at the interface of α- and β-tubulin (Fig. 3). However, as shown in the ligplot, the binding modes inside the binding cavity are unique (Fig. 3). It has different binding modalities, as different functional groups are substituted in the scaffold structure. In the context of docking scores, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos interacts more firmly with tubulin residues than other derivatives do. Its binding involves two hydrogen bonds with Val355 (bond length 3.91 Å) and Ser178 (bond length 3.36 Å & 3.11 Å), whereas the lead molecule noscapiine shows only one hydrogen bond with Tyr224 (bond length 3.16 Å) (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Results of the molecular docking of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapine with tubulin. It showed better docking scores and affinity towards tubulin than did noscapine.

Ligands ID	Glide XP _{score} (Kcal/mol)	Glide Lipo (Kcal/mol)	Glide Evdw (Kcal/mol)	Glide Ecoul (Kcal/mol)	Glide Emodel (Kcal/mol)	Glide Energy (Kcal/mol)
N-3-bromobenzyl	-6.727	-3.917	-39.148	-0.582	-47.061	-39.731
Noscapine	-4.080	-2.000	-27.696	-7.820	-45.461	-35.516

Fig. 1: a) RMSD of the C α carbon atoms of tubulin alone and in complex with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos during 100 ns of MD simulation. During the entire simulation period, the RMSD of the C α atoms showed very small relative fluctuations (0.21 to 2.24 Å), indicating the stability of the complex. b) Time evolution of the Rg of tubulin in complex with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos after 100 ns of MD simulation. During the entire simulation period, the molecular systems were stable.

Fig. 2a&b RMSF of the tubulin residues in both the bound and unbound states of the tubulin heterodimer with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. The flexibility levels of the residues varied between the free and ligand-bound forms of tubulin. All the amino acids showed very low fluctuations (1.5 to 3.5 Å), suggesting the rigidity of the residues in both the free and bound forms of tubulin.

Fig. 3

N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapine are well encased within the binding site, i.e., at the interface of α - and β -tubulin. The macromodel surface approach based on α - and β -tubulin (brown denotes α -tubulin, and magenta denotes β -tubulin) shows the binding site. Two-dimensional illustration of the interaction between N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapine with the binding site residues of tubulin. The dashed lines are the hydrogen bonds and bond lengths in Å. The representation of hydrophobic interactions is an arc with radial spokes. LIGPLOT software was used to create the figures. Only the residues that were 5 Å away from the docked ligands are shown.

The predictive binding free energy ($\Delta G_{bind, PBSA}$) of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapine with tubulin is shown in Table 2 and was determined via the MM-PBSA approach. For each tubulin-noscapinoid complex, the binding free energy value was determined in accordance with the mean value of 1000 snapshots taken during the last 2 ns of the MD trajectory. N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos has a stronger binding affinity with tubulin than does

noscapine, with the highest binding energy of -25.50 kcal/mol. The intermolecular van der Waals (ΔE_{vdw}) and electrostatic (ΔE_{elec}) interactions are excellent contributors to binding, whereas the polar solvation terms (ΔG_{polar}) counteract binding. The solvent accessible surface area term (ΔG_{SASA}), nevertheless, contributed favourably but marginally.

Table 2. Predictive binding free energy calculated (Kcal/mol) for N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos and noscapine with the $\alpha\beta$ tubulin dimer.

Complex	ΔE_{vdw} (Kcal/mol)	ΔE_{elec} (Kcal/mol)	ΔG_{polar} (Kcal/mol)	ΔG_{SASA} (Kcal/mol)	$\Delta G_{binding}$ (Kcal/mol)
N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine	-41.51	-20.46	42.51	-6.04	- 25.50
Noscapine	-36.56	-22.90	40.65	-4.12	- 22.93

3.2 Cell viability assay

We evaluated the antiproliferative activity of noscapine and its derivative, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos, against two distinct breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7 &

MDA-MB-231). In addition, a normal cell line, HEK-231, was also used to observe the effects of both molecules on normal healthy cells. The viability of the cancer cells was found to decrease in a dose-dependent manner. Surprisingly, the percentage of viable normal healthy

cells was reduced. The IC_{50} values calculated for noscapine and its derivative, N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos, were $47.0 \pm 1.651 \mu\text{M}$ and $12.12 \pm 0.911 \mu\text{M}$ against the MDA-MB-231 cell line, whereas against the MCF7 cell line, the IC_{50} values were they were $27.0 \pm 1.29 \mu\text{M}$ and $7.51 \pm 0.68 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. In contrast, the IC_{50} values

of noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos against the normal HEK-231 cell line were very high, such as $284.3 \pm 2.19 \mu\text{M}$ and $215 \pm 2.19 \mu\text{M}$, respectively. The MTT assay revealed that noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos have strong cytotoxic effects on breast cancer cells compared with healthy cells (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Cytotoxic effects of noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos against the breast cancer cell lines **a)** MCF-7 and **b)** MDA-MB-231 revealed a reduction in cell survival in a dose-dependent manner. **c)** In contrast, the normal healthy cell line (HEK) is well protected by treatment with noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. All the experiments were carried out in triplicate, and the data are reported as the means \pm standard deviations ($n = 3$).

3.3 Flow cytometry analysis for the apoptosis assay

Apoptosis in a triple-negative breast cancer cell line was evaluated after treatment with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. During apoptosis, there is a change in the lipid composition, i.e., the phosphatidylserine translocated from the inner leaflet to the outer leaflet. Phosphatidylserine translocation to the outer membrane was detected by annexin V binding. Using fluorescent dyes, early and late apoptotic cells were quantified by FACS. The percentages of early apoptotic and late

apoptotic cells after treatment with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos at an IC_{50} concentration ($12.12 \mu\text{M}$) for 72 h are shown in Figure 5. Only a few early (0.01%) and necrotic (0.39%) apoptotic cells observed in the control after 72 h were considered background cell death due to regular stress (Fig. 5). In contrast, there were significantly more early apoptotic cells (63.86%) and late apoptotic cells (10.06% and 5.18% necrotic cells) after treatment with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos than in the control untreated cells (Fig. 5).

Fig 5: Flow cytometry analysis of apoptotic MDA-MB-231 cells treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos at an IC₅₀ concentration (12.12 μ M) for 72 hours and compared with nontreated control cells. The three subpopulations, PI-negative and Alexa Fluor 488-negative viable cells with intact membranes and preserved amino-phospholipid asymmetry (PI-, Alexa Fluor 488-), PI-negative and Alexa Fluor 488-positive early apoptotic cells with intact cellular membranes exposing phosphatidylserine (PI-Alexa Fluor 488+), and PI-positive and Alexa Fluor 488-positive late apoptotic cells with compromised asymmetry and membrane permeability (PI+, Alexa Fluor 488+), were differentiated by the use of an Alexa Fluor 488 conjugate of Annexin-V along with propidium iodide (PI) dye. The data are representative of three independent experiments. (B) Percentages of viable (Q3), early apoptotic (Q1), late apoptotic (Q2) and necrotic (Q4) cells measured via flow cytometry.

3.4 Reactive oxygen species

An increase in intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS) induces cell death, as it is associated with nucleic acid damage, disturbance of the mitochondrial membrane potential, and organelle failure, all of which point to the start of apoptosis. The DCFDA test was used to measure the intracellular ROS levels. Bright green

fluorescence in the cells treated with the IC₅₀ concentrations of noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos revealed that the ROS level was much higher than that in the control group, indicating that ROS may play a role in the induction of apoptosis. Imaging was performed using fluorescence microscopy (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 Detection of ROS formation in the cancer cell line MDA-MB-231 after treatment with noscapine and N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos by DCFDA assay. The bright intensity of green fluorescence indicated a high amount of ROS within the cell, indicating the potential involvement of ROS in programmed cell death.

3.5 Mitochondrial membrane potential

One of the main factors contributing to mitochondrial damage is the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) within the cell. Thus, we wanted to evaluate the effect of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos treatment of MDA-MB-231 cells on mitochondrial damage, as it

induces the generation of ROS within the cells. When the mitochondria are damaged, a decrease in the membrane potential occurs, which can be detected by a catalytic JC-1 fluorescent dye. In the untreated cells, the JC-1 dye exhibited potential-dependent accumulation in the

mitochondria and produced red fluorescence, while treatment with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos changed the fluorescence from red to green, indicating a change in

the mitochondrial membrane potential due to injury (Fig 7).

Fig. 7 Changes in the mitochondrial membrane potential was detected by fluorescence imaging (JC-1 test). Untreated cells serve as control cells with healthy mitochondria; cells treated with the drug demonstrate a shift in fluorescence emission from red to green because of damage to the mitochondrial membrane; this dye may accumulate in mitochondria in a dependent manner.

3.6 Cellular observation using acridine orange, DAPI, and ethidium bromide staining

The characteristics of apoptotic cells include the formation of apoptotic bodies, chromatin condensation, cellular shrinkage, and membrane blebbing, which are essential morphological alterations associated with programmed cell death. We used DAPI, EtBr, and AO

staining to confirm that N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine induced apoptosis. The treated cells displayed several apoptotic characteristics, such as membrane blebbing, fragmented nuclei, and the appearance of apoptotic bodies. However, the untreated cells retained their standard shape. The intensity of fluorescence was also greater than that in the untreated group (Fig 8).

Fig 8 Induction of apoptosis in MDA-MB-231 cells by N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos treatment as visualized through AO, EtBr, and EtBr staining. In the treated group, the fluorescence intensity was greater than that in the untreated group, whereas the untreated cells maintained their typical morphology.

3.7 Colony formation assay

We next performed the inhibition to colony formation using the breast cancer cell line MDA-MB-231 to further establish the antiproliferative efficacy of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. The cancer cells were treated at the IC₅₀ (12.12 μM) and IC₇₀ (19.41 μM) concentrations and incubated under culture conditions for 10 days for

colony formation. The number of colonies formed was determined via ImageJ software. Compared with that in the untreated group, colony formation in the treated group was significantly lower (Fig 9). The number of colonies treated with the IC₅₀ and IC₇₀ concentrations decreased by 58% and 86%, respectively.

Fig. 9 N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos effects on the clonogenicity assay show that it inhibits the growth of MDA-MB-231 cells into colonies. The data are presented as the means ± SDs; the graph with n = 3.

3.8 Cell migration assay

In the cell migration assay, the MDA-MB-231 cells treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos exhibited decreased migration at 24 and 48 hours, and images of the scratches were captured using a microscope. The proportion of the wound thickness was measured with GraphPad Prism.

Compared with that of the treated cells, the gap thickness of the wounds in the untreated control cells decreased (Fig. 10). The results revealed that the chemical drug inhibited cell migration in a concentration-dependent manner, increasing the wound gap in treated cells.

Fig 10 A wound-healing assay demonstrated that N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos suppressed the migration of MDA-MB-231 cells. The relative thickness of the wound was quantified using GraphPad Prism, and the data are expressed as the means ± SDs from three independent experiments.

3.9 Spheroid fabrication and characterization

We determined the effect of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos on an established spheroid using MDA-MB-231 cells. The spheroids were treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos at the

IC₅₀ concentration for 24 h and 48 h. The volume of the spheroids was significantly reduced after 24 h and 48 h of treatment, possibly because of the inhibition of proliferation and induction of apoptosis in cancer cells with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos treatment (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 The developed spheroid using the MDA-MB-231 cell line was treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos for 24 h and 48 h. The volume of the spheroid was significantly reduced due to treatment with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos.

4. DISCUSSION

According to earlier reports, noscapine and its derivatives bind to tubulin, alter microtubule dynamics both in vitro and in vivo and inhibit cell division specifically in cancer cells, followed by the induction of apoptosis (Ye *et al.*, 1998; Landen *et al.*, 2002; Zhou, Gupta, *et al.*, 2002; Zhou, Panda, *et al.*, 2002; Checchi *et al.*, 2003; Zhou *et al.*, 2003; Aneja, Vangapandu, Lopus, Chandra, *et al.*, 2006; Aneja, Vangapandu, Lopus, Visweswarappa, *et al.*, 2006; Joshi *et al.*, 2010). However, its derivatives, known as noscapinoids, are considered more potent at inhibiting cell proliferation and induction of apoptosis. In continuation of our efforts to make more effective derivatives, in this study, we report another derivative, namely, N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine. It is always a challenge to synthesize noscapine derivatives

because of their sensitive C–C bonds. The reaction conditions used in this study do not influence the sensitive C–C bond connecting two heterocyclic phthalide and isoquinoline units (reaction scheme 1). The molecule was synthesized in good yield and was characterized with NMR, IR and mass spectral data.

The biological activity of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was studied experimentally in terms of its antiproliferative activity in two human breast cancer cell lines, MDA-MB-231 (a triple-negative human breast cancer cell line) and MCF-7 (a triple-positive human breast cancer cell line), and it inhibited spheroid formation and induced apoptosis. The antiproliferative activity was found to be dose dependent, i.e., the percentage of inhibition of cell multiplication increased with increasing concentrations of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos (Fig. 4).

The wide difference in IC₅₀ values obtained using MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 cells suggests that the compound inhibits the proliferation of cancer cells in a cell type-dependent manner. This potent derivative was further used to investigate the mechanism of action more precisely. The induction of apoptosis by N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was studied by imaging with three fluorescent dyes, AO, EtBr, and DAPI (Fig. 8). FACS analysis was also used to determine the percentage of apoptotic cells. The apoptotic process is defined biochemically by changes in the lipid composition of the cell membrane. Phosphatidylserine, which is typically found on the inner leaflet of the cell membrane, translocates to the outer leaflet and is recognized by annexin V binding. Propidium iodide, a cell-impermeant DNA-binding fluorescent dye, can only enter cells when they are in the late stages of apoptosis and when membrane permeability is weakened. When the MDA-MB-231 cell line was treated with the IC₅₀ concentration for 72 hours, the percentages of early and late apoptotic cells were 63.86 and 10.06%, respectively, which were significantly greater than those of untreated cells (Fig. 5). We assessed the degree of reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation in cancer cells to elucidate the mechanism of apoptosis induction. High levels of ROS damage the microtubule network, resulting in the loss of mitochondrial membrane integrity and cell death (Nambiar *et al.*, 2020). Compared with normal cells, cancer cells have more ROS when treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos than normal cells (Fig. 6), and increasing the ROS level might selectively kill cancer cells (Pelicano *et al.*, 2004). In general, tumor cells propagate to different parts of the body by colonization. Thus, investigating the ability of drugs to inhibit the colonization of tumor cells is useful. Using a colony formation assay, we found that N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos inhibited the colony-forming potential of MDA-MB-231 cells (Fig. 9). Furthermore, recent research has suggested that spheroids are valuable models for studying metastasis and epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT), as well as for use in tumors. Additionally, multicellular spheroids have been widely used as platforms for drug screening because of their ability to mimic the structural organization of solid tumors. In this study, 3D multicellular spheroids were generated from MDA-MB-231 cells and treated with N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos. It was observed that N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos significantly

inhibited the growth of the spheroids. Although noscapine, the parent lead molecule, is currently undergoing clinical trials, its derivative, N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine, is advantageous over noscapine because of its enhanced potency without compromising the nontoxic profile of noscapine.

5. CONCLUSION

Noscapinoids, as derivatives of noscapine, represent a promising class of anticancer molecules with multiple mechanisms of action, including microtubule inhibition, apoptosis induction, antiangiogenic, and anti-inflammatory properties. To increase the therapeutic potential of the parent molecule, noscapine, we aimed to develop a potent analogue of noscapine. We have provided the simplest methods for direct and regioselective modification of the noscapine scaffold to produce the N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine derivative in high yields. Molecular docking studies revealed that the newly designed N-3-bromobenzyl-noscapine has better binding affinity towards tubulin. The anticancer activity of N3-Br-Benzyl-Nos was evaluated in two human breast cancer cell lines, which exhibited potent cytotoxicity without causing side effects in a normal cell line (HEK). Therefore, these novel compounds may prove efficacious not only in the treatment of breast carcinoma but also for other types of cancer. Our results compel us to continue to examine the effects of these novel compounds in animal model with the final goal of being useful for human clinical studies.

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Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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